

**Design of aluminium alloys suitable for
additive manufacturing**

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- Introduction: Aluminium alloys and AM
- Experimental procedure:
 - Gas atomization
 - Gleeble physical simulator
- Results: Al-Fe-Cr alloy
- Conclusions

Aluminium alloys for AM

Material problems related to the additive manufacturing of aluminium alloys:

- The number of commercially available (and processable) alloys is limited
 - Hardenable Al10SiMg
 - Eutectic AlSi12
 - Hardenable AlMgSc
- The currently used materials in AM technologies have originally been developed for totally different manufacturing technologies (e.g. casting, forging)
 - Many Al alloys are hardly weldable
 - Some high strength alloys contain highly volatile elements (e.g. Zn)
 - Aluminium has a High reflectivity, low viscosity etc.
- Optimization of the composition will be necessary
 - There will be variants of already existing alloys
 - There will be new alloy compositions

Aluminium alloys for AM

Age-hardening alloys

Al-Cu (2xxx)

Al-Mg-Si (6xxx)

Al-Zn-Mg-Cu (7xxx)

$$\tau_{or} = \frac{G \cdot b}{\lambda}$$

AM = rapid solidification + heat treatment

Cooling rates: $10^3 - 10^8$ K/s

Thermal gradients: $10^3 - 10^4$ K/m

7000 series after 3D printing
Large columnar grains with cracks

J.H. Martin *et al*, Nature 549 (2017) 365

Aluminium alloys containing transition elements?

Diffusion coefficient (D) of transition elements in aluminium matrix

Element	D (cm ² /s)	Element	D (cm ² /s)
Cu	4.8×10^{-9}	Fe	3.8×10^{-10}
Mg	2.1×10^{-8}	Mn	2.5×10^{-11}
Zn	1.6×10^{-8}	Co	8.4×10^{-9}
Si	1.6×10^{-8}	Ni	8.1×10^{-9}
Cr	1.3×10^{-12}	Zr	2.4×10^{-12}

Al 7075 (~45 μm) coated with 1%vol hydrogenated-stabilized Zr nanoparticles

AM: Crack-free, small equiaxed grains

Formation of Al₃Zr nucleant phase

Al-Fe-Cr alloys

Rapid solidification (“*Melt spinning*”)

Microstructure (TEM)

Mechanical properties

INTRODUCTION

Aluminium alloys for AM

The aim of this work is to explore whether aluminium alloys containing transition elements (Al-Fe-Cr) and processed by gas atomization could be potential alloy families for AM

⇒ As-cast Al-Fe-Cr alloy (Al-8.12 wt% Fe-5.04 wt% Cr)

Arc melting and gas atomization

Gleeble Physical Simulator

*Graphite matrix containing Al
powders ($d < 45 \mu\text{m}$) for sintering*

Inert gas atomization

Particle size distribution

Argon atomized Al-Fe-Cr particles (Three particle sizes)

Argon atomized Al-Fe-Cr particles ($< 45 \mu\text{m}$)

Argon atomized Al-Fe-Cr particles

45-100 μm

100-150 μm

Composition (EDX)

Al-Fe-Cr alloy (Al-8.12 wt% Fe-5.04 wt% Cr)

45-100 μm

Element. Spectrum	Al (wt%)	Fe (wt%)	Cr (wt%)
1	86.3	8.7	5.1
2	88.2	7.3	4.5
3	86.7	8.2	5.1
4	86.2	8.5	5.3
5	86.7	8.4	4.9
6	87.4	7.9	4.7
7	84.8	9.2	6
8	87.5	7.5	5
Average	86.7 \pm1.0	8.2\pm0.6	5.1\pm0.4

Phase analysis of atomized powders (XRD)

Nanoindentation and mechanical properties

High Load (25-90 mN)

Sintering simulation using the Gleeble technology

Graphite matrix containing Al powders ($d < 45 \mu\text{m}$) for sintering

SEM micrograph corresponding to the AlFeCr powder ($< 45 \mu\text{m}$) after consolidation

- Aluminium alloys containing transition elements (Al-Fe-Cr), traditionally studied and processed by rapid solidification techniques, show very high strength and thermal stability due to precipitation of finely dispersed phases.
- The solidification rates involved in AM, comparable to these involved in rapid solidification techniques, suggest that these alloys could be suitable feedstock for AM.
- Gas atomized powders with a particle size smaller than 45 μm , which is suitable for SLM possess high mechanical strength due to precipitation of icosahedral quasicrystalline particles.
- Gleeble technology has been considered to analyze rapid solidification processes of Al alloys, however, the low cooling and heating rates of the graphite matrix used to simulate sintering conditions during AM prevented a thorough characterization of the densification potential of this alloy.

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